

DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE PLAY AREAS FOR SCHOOL AGE
CHILDREN

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Abstract: Based on the obtained theoretical and empirical data, development and testing of a program for the development of the cognitive sphere of preschool children through game activities.

Key word: Preschool children, pedagogy, psychology, cognitive.

INTRODUCTION

Modern society especially needs people with a high level of general education and professional training who can solve complex economic, political, social, scientific and technical problems. The cognitive sphere is a socially important quality of a person and is formed in the activity. The phenomenon of the cognitive field attracts the attention of many scientists as one of the important factors of learning. To reveal the essence and meaning of this concept, it is necessary to start with a scientific definition of the term "cognitive sphere". According to the encyclopedic dictionary of psychology and pedagogy, the cognitive field is "cognitive processes: intuition, perception, memory, thinking, imagination." A synonym of this definition is the cognitive domain. At this age, the child's cognitive activity has its own characteristics, and the primary image of the surrounding world is born in preschool age. The image of the world is formed and exists in the process of the emergence, development and activity of a person's cognitive sphere, and we consider it a complex formation that ensures the normal and full intellectual and emotional existence and development of a person. personality in the world. The possibilities of learning in preschool age are virtually limitless. An inquisitive child is the initiator of increasing his knowledge base thanks to the frequently asked questions and understandable answers of parents and

teachers. Active children learn through interaction with adults and peers, and through experience to the extent that others allow experience and action. But the characteristics of the development of the cognitive sphere of a preschool child are such that the mental processes aimed at knowing are mainly not voluntary. For comprehensive development, parents and teachers should direct the child's attention, interest and activity. And this should be used not only in developmental lessons in a preschool, but also in everyday communication with children.

The concept of "developing environment" was introduced by George Raven as an area of competence development. "In such an environment, - J. According to Raven, "people have the opportunity to develop their skills while pursuing and achieving goals that interest them." The environment should be a source of enrichment for children's activities. All children need a joyful environment from the first day in preschool (hereinafter referred to as kindergarten). Complete childhood is its own private territory, a place equipped with love, understanding of the age, heart and aspirations of each child. Under the right conditions, under the guidance of the teacher, the child becomes the designer of this space. One of the main conditions for creating an environment that develops the subject in the group is to rely on a person-oriented model of interaction between the educator and children, that is, "the educator is not close, not above, but with the children. at the level of their eyes."

The environment that develops the topic in the group should be dynamic and change depending on the age, individual characteristics of the children, the time of year and the topics being studied. It should ensure the creation of certain centers (corners, zones) depending on the program, education and upbringing of children (see pictures, play, exercise, etc.) -do not interfere with one, and also move at will from one activity center to another, from quiet activity to active activity.

Group rooms must be equipped according to the height of children, and all toys and materials must be certified. Depending on the area of the group rooms, the needs and interests of the children, their preferences, the teacher himself

determines the number of cells (centers, zones, corners), their location and connection area. It is known that a game environment with an empty and colorless theme has a negative effect on children, which in turn "slows down" the development of the individual. Oversaturation of the subject environment also has a negative effect on the mental state of children.

Only an organized object-game environment that is repeated periodically, highly variable and satisfies interest can have a developing effect and stimulate children's mental processes to active cognitive activity. Children of preschool age are very mobile, so the space should be freer, and a corner with sports equipment should be allocated. To transform such playrooms, teachers create different "movement" paths. Performing various exercises: walking, crawling, overcoming obstacles.

Role-playing games are typical of middle age. A distinctive feature of these games is the use of substitute objects that recreate the general idea in a playful way, for example, you can make a cake from a constructor and feed it to a doll. Such uniqueness in games plays a big role in the intellectual development of children, imagination develops. Children of preschool age are also interested in language, and accordingly, play activities should be supplemented with various didactic materials: let children play with various building materials for construction, and it is also important to conduct all kinds of activities. experiments with children.

It is necessary to encourage cognitive activity in older age groups - offer children to solve puzzles, read them various encyclopedias and illustrated publications, look at children's magazines, repeat fairy tales, riddles and riddles, etc. In the playroom, you should choose a corner for didactic material, which allows children to choose their games at any time.

HOME: "Magic wands in the hands of magicians"

Creating motivation and mood for joint activity "Smile". Children stand in a circle and pronounce words, perform actions. I am your friend. (smile)

Conclusion: Thus, the cognitive sphere is creativity, independence, initiative in the process of activity, as well as the desire to understand, understand, learn, find, feel

the joy of success from an independently found way to solve a problem or problem.

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